

SCHOOL-COMMUNITY PARTNERSHIP, STAKEHOLDER'S WORK COMMITMENT AND CONFLICT MANAGEMENT IN IMPROVING SCHOOL PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to determine the correlation between school-community partnership, stakeholder's work commitment, and conflict management in improving school performance in Lakeside District, Division of San Pablo City. The descriptive-correlational quantitative research design was adopted and statistical tools such as Pearson r were utilized to test the relationship of the independent and dependent variables. Hypotheses were tested and the findings revealed that there is no significant relationship between school performance and school-community partnership, stakeholder's work commitment, and conflict management practices. Having those findings this study recommends the alliance of parents and teachers as regard to the improvement of school plan and facilities, resource generation, community mobilization, and personal & professional growth; consider having collaboration as regard to organization, work ethics, job involvement, and personal and professional growth; technical assistance through training, workshop, coaching, and mentoring on the school-community partnership, stakeholder's work commitment, and conflict management practices; and the conduct of other related researches in the future.

Keywords: school-community partnership, stakeholder's work commitment, conflict management, and school performance.